

Assessing Awareness and Adoption of Digital Technologies among Rural Communities

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ABSTRACT

The information super highway otherwise called the internet and other digital technologies like hurricane have dived into every aspect of human activities relying on information with rural communities inclusive which invariably include rural development and food security and as a result a better understanding of existing information practices and socio-technical processes is a sine-qua-non in rural areas if digital based projects are to be effective. This study therefore is an investigation into the Level of awareness and utilization of digital technologies by rural dwellers. The study adopted descriptive survey design with a sampled population of 400 rural dwellers selected through purposive random sampling techniques and drawn from 24 rural communities in 6 local governed areas in Ebonyi State, Nigeria which include Abakaliki, Izzi, Ishielu, Ohaozara, Ohaukwu and Afikpo North. The principle instrument used for data collection is a self-designed four point structured questionnaire. The questionnaires were personally administered with the assistance of each community youth leaders. Data collected were analyzed using frequency and percentages while the analyzed data were displayed in charts and tables. The result of the study revealed among other things that that most dwellers of the rural communities studied are too far from the digital ecosystem as the data reveal that the people are highly unaware of the existence of most contemporary digital information technologies and that most digital information technologies and sources are highly unavailable for the rural dwellers to utilize. The study then suggest inter-alia that all identified constraints in the utilization of digital information sources, facilities and gadgets by rural dwellers should be tackled by government and her concerned agencies head-on in line with the mandate of Nigerian Communication Commission (NCC) which is to promote the provision of modern, universal, efficient, reliable, affordable and easily accessible communication services and the widest range thereof throughout Nigeria and that government with her agency should provide mandatory ICT training program designed for both male and female rural dwellers regardless of the occupation with a view to increasing their economic wellbeing through the acquisition of technology skills thereby making them relevant in the digital ecosystem.

Keywords: Digital Technology, Rural Dwellers, Rural Community, Information, United Nations-Sustainable Development Goals, Library, Information and Communication Technology

1.0. INTRODUCTION

A run-down on the United Nations-Sustainable Development Goals (UN-SDGs) which encompasses 17 goals that expressed the desire and eagerness by various governments of the world to get rid of poverty and hunger and to provide quality education, good health, gender inequality, good jobs and economic growth and partnership among international communities, leave no one in doubt that the focus should be on rural dwellers as the goals respond to the world's most development challenge.

As argued by Igbuzor (2006), the purpose of development is to improve people's lives by expanding their choices, freedom, and dignity. In the rural areas of the world, these seem to be a mirage. All the same, it is believed that the provision of vital information or knowledge should be a starting point in the transformative agenda of the SDGs which must be harnessed to the fullest (Onwubiko, 2021) as access to information, internet and computer services will increase the people's knowledge on various opportunities available more so as they relate to SDGs 1-6, 9, 11 and 13 as the UN-SDGs recognized the interdependence between growth, poverty eradication and sustainable development so that achieving one of them can be expected to contribute in achieving others, for instance, poverty eradication would definitely assist in handling health and education challenges as well as achieving health and education goals would also contribute to fighting against poverty.

In this digital era, characterized by digital technologies, development is measured by the availability and utilization of digital sources of information which determine the level of development. Regrettably, the dynamics of globalization and the emergence of digital technologies under the umbrella of information and communication technologies have metamorphosed in a tidal wave of information which presently has overwhelmed many nations of the world in the last decades and the case has even heightened with the birth of Artificial intelligence and associated technologies. This development has ultimately changed the educational needs of individuals as well as the society at large and this has given rise to special demand for additional specialty in the acquisition of knowledge. Against this backdrop Ahsanullah (2002) posited that modern digital technologies are sources for development of wealth and power when they are directed towards the well being of humanity. This implies that digital technologies as of today are engine for sustainable development and global competitiveness.

The underlying factor is that the information super highway otherwise called the internet and other digital technologies like hurricane have dived into every aspect of human activities relying on information with rural communities inclusive which invariably noted O' farrel (1999) include rural development and food security and as a result a better understanding of existing information practices and socio-technical processes is a sine-qua-non in rural areas if digital based projects are to be effective. In this regard, Accascina (2000) hinted how ICTs directly or indirectly affect poverty alleviation, more so in to rural development and food security such as in the delivery of market or employment information or the creation of well paid jobs that eventually trickle down to rural communities.

The most common definition applied by international organizations to separate rural and urban regions is that developed by the Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD) (2006). The definition distinguishes two hierarchical levels of territorial unit: local and regional. At local community level the OECD defines rural areas as communities with a population density below 150 inhabitants per square kilometer. At regional level, the OECD distinguishes larger functional or administrative units by their degree of rurality, depending on what share of the region's population lives in rural communities. Rural areas or rural communities and dwellers are simply put are those part of a

nation that are under-developed and still practice high traditional lifestyle and behavioral-wise guided by their culture which cannot be found in urban areas. As buttressed by Udoka (1998) and Anaeto and Anaeto (2010), when the term rural is mentioned in Africa, the picture is that of an area with acute under-development and poverty epitomized in the form of deplorable road condition, lack of portable drinking water, poor housing, poor sanitation, and high level of illiteracy. It also brings to mind, geographical locations in Africa with populations of hungry, wretched looking people, stunted in nature and kwashiorkor riddled children. It also conjures image of a people who suffer in the farms from morning to evening with no commensurate harvest. Rural areas therefore are such areas that lack basic human necessities such as hospitals, banks, good schools and electricity.

Suffice it to say, that dwellers of such rural areas just like their counterparts in urban areas need information about the happenings in the wider society and how to live a better life. As revealed by Anibueze (2005), there is high level of ignorance in the rural areas apart from the poor physical development as such need to be empowered with information (knowledge) of the fundamentals of population and development. This is built on the premise that a rural dweller constitutes a nuisance if not exposed to accurate information such as information on modern family needs, nutrition, women rights, and child right among others. To this end, Asemah (2011) infers that rural dwellers need accurate information that will enable them to live and appreciate the activities of the government in power after all, they are involved in the task of feeding the nation, therefore need information on several issues including information on loan opportunities offered by government and how to dispose their farm proceeds as well as information about health care, weather, family planning, agricultural inputs among others. The bottom line is that with the availability of relevant well coordinated information, the rural dwellers will have confidence and trust in government and the society at large.

The submission is that for any nation let alone rural community to develop, it needs to have and provide relevant, updated and adequate information on food security, democracy, health, education, gender equality among others (Onwubiko, 2021). Invariably, obtaining quality education is the foundation of improving people's lives and sustainable development. With ICTs being handy tools for obtaining information, the presumption is that it is accessible to all and with it, users can obtain information from various sources in any part of the world and that one computer could meet the needs of a large rural community. Information and communication Technology infrastructure help people develop the capacity to effectively use information and preserve information to ensure ongoing access for future generation. The implication is that the emergence of ICTs as the bedrock of digital technology powered by computers leading to geometrical growth in information with the maxim, the world is a global village, that with a keystroke, the globe is at your disposal as one could lay hand on any sort of information online. To many especially those from urban areas and developed nation as a whole, the assertion may be factual but to the man in the rural area, how factual is the assertion? However, it is disheartening to state based on available data, that half of the world population lacks access to information online regardless of IFLAs consistent position that access to information is essential in achieving SDGs (IFLA, 2018).

As expressed by Article 19 (2018), information access is essential for individuals and communities to engage government to improve public services, citizens to know their rights to public services and what resources are available to them as well as monitoring how effectively governments and authorities are providing vital services and holding them to account. Access to information is also necessary as with it, communities will be able to participate in decision making processes for water and other service provision. In the same vein UNESCO (2022) declares that access to Information is a key driver for the achievement of the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable development, and in particular SDG Goal 16 that promotes just, peaceful and inclusive societies. Access to information is critical for empowering the public to make decisions, holding governments accountable, evaluating public officials in implementing and monitoring the SDGs and facilitating effective public participation. Open and inclusive access to Information empowers people and lays the foundations for building inclusive knowledge societies. As asserted by UN-SDGs (2022) Target 11.1 by 2030, government should ensure access for all to adequate, safe and affordable housing and basic services and upgrade slums.

The assertion is that Nigeria as a nation just like many developing nation is embracing the contemporary technologies with exponential utilization of mobile phones popularly called GSM providing communication which in the past was unimaginable. As far as 2002, Olukoya did state that about a million people have mobile phones, but internet use is lagging behind with only an estimated 20,000 to 30,000 Nigerians connected to the internet. The reason behind this is not far-fetched as over 120 million Nigerians are rural dwellers who can be said by implication excluded from partaking in the emerging information economy thereby not in reality with what is happening in the digital ecosystem. Twenty two years after this assertion, can one emphatically say, that the story has changed in the rural areas of Nigeria after all one may say, that Nigerians including rural dwellers are witnessing the presence of mobile communication masts being installed by mobile communication companies like Glo, Airtel, MTN and 9 Mobile and as at March, 2024 there are 219,005, 878 mobile GSM subscribers in Nigeria (Nigerian Communication Commission, 2024). Going down the memory lane, Adimorah (1990) in a research reports that 80% of illiterate rural dwellers wallow in information deprivation. Is this report still relevant or has it been overtaken by events or do we assume that the installations of masts have made the difference?

It is to find an answer to these puzzles that this study became imperative. This study will be limited to ascertaining the level of awareness of certain digital technologies and the availability of common and easy to handle digital information communication gadgets such as laptops, desktops, GSM, Smart phones, radios, televisions, internet modem and smart television/decoders. Generally the objectives of this study include

- I. To ascertain the level of awareness of certain digital information technologies in rural areas in Ebonyi State,
- II. To determine the availability of common and easy to handle digital information communication gadgets in rural areas in Ebonyi State,
- III. To determine the accessibility of these sources of information

- IV. To ascertain the reason behind their utilization and
- V. To identify challenges faced in using these digital information technologies by the rural dwellers.

2.0. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey design with a sampled population of 400 rural dwellers selected through purposive random sampling techniques and drawn from 24 rural communities in 6 local governed areas in Ebonyi State, Nigeria which include Abakaliki, Izzi, Ishielu, Ohaozara, Ohaukwu and Afikpo North. In Abakaliki Local Government the four communities are, Azuiyokwu, Ndiagu, Amachi-Unuhu and Agbaja, in Izzi we have, Iboko, Iziogo, Oswanka and Nkwegu, in Ohaukwu are, Effium, Ndiakparata, Amofia-Ngbo and Izhia, Ohaozara, the communities include, Okposi, Obioha, Uburu and Ishiegu, while in Ishielu are Ezillo, Umuahali, Ezzaegu and Ohaofia-Agba and Afikpo North LG are Ngodo, Ozizza, Akpoha and Nkpohoro. The principle instrument used for data collection is a self-designed four point structured questionnaire. The questionnaires were personally administered with the assistance of each community youth leaders which made it possible for the entire questionnaire to be returned 100%. Data collected were analyzed using frequency and percentages while the analyzed data were displayed in charts and tables.

3.0. PRESENTATION OF DATA

Part 1: Demographic Data

Figure 1: Ages of Respondents

As displayed in figure 1 above 47% representing 140 of the 300 respondents were of the ages of 18-34 while 123 respondents or 41% were between 35 to 54 years of age and the remaining 12% representing 37 respondents were of the ages of 55 and above.

Figure 2: Gender of Respondents

The data in figure 2 reveal that majority of the respondents were male representing 67.33% or 202 out of the 300 respondents. This is because in these communities, men are at liberty to associate freely unlike the female folk that were only 98 or 32.67% that need approval before getting involved in the research work.

Figure 3: Distribution of Respondents by Educational Qualification

The figure above gives a breakdown of respondents based on educational qualification. The data as analyzed show that 122 respondents or 40.67 which is in the majority hold secondary school certificate, followed by those with first school leaving certificate, 37.33% or 112 respondents while those with degree took the rear with 5.33% representing 16 respondents. It is surprising to note that 32 respondents or 10.67% were stack illiterate that they can neither read nor write even some of them with first school leaving certificate can neither read nor write.

Figure 4: Distribution of respondents by Occupation

The spread of the data in figure 4 indicate that majority of the rural dwellers are farmers as 115 of the respondents or 38.33% were farmers, followed by commercial motorcycle riders popularly called Okada which is a lucrative occupation in rural communities as it serves as an important means of transportation among the rural dwellers with 65 respondents or 21.67%, 43 or 14.33% are petty traders with 11% or 33 respondents as artisans. Others are civil servants, 19 or 6.33%, teachers, 4.33% or 13 respondents and those involved in fishing with only 4% representing 12 respondents.

Part 2: Awareness and Utilization of Digital Information Technologies Data

Table 1: Level of Awareness of contemporary digital technologies

Item	HA		A		UA		HUA		Mean(X)	Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
computer	32	10.67	112	37.33	56	18.67	100	33.33	2.25	UA
Internet	37	12.33	94	31.33	106	35.33	63	21	2.35	UA
Modem	10	3.33	32	10.67	114	38	144	48	1.69	HUA
Block chain	8	2.67	-	-	95	31.67	197	65.67	1.40	HUA
Cloud computing	6	2	-	-	-	-	294	98	1.06	HUA
Artificial intelligence	3	1	18	6	88	29.33	191	63.67	1.44	HUA
I-phone	47	15.67	13	4.33	80	26.67	160	53.33	1.82	HUA
Smart phones	53	17.67	4	1.33	99	33	144	48	1.89	HUA
Digital library	23	7.67	6	2	130	43.33	141	47	1.70	HUA
Database	23	7.67	6	2	130	43.33	141	47	1.70	HUA

*Key> HA=Highly Aware, A=aware, UA=Unaware, HUA=Highly Unaware, Benchmark=2.50

The data as collected and displayed in table 1 revealed that all the items in the table fall below the mean benchmark of 2.50. The data show that over 70% of the respondents indicated that that they are highly unaware of contemporary digital information technologies such as the modem, block-chain, cloud

computing, artificial intelligence, I-phones, smart phones, digital library and database while only 144 respondents or 48% indicated that they are highly aware or aware of computers and 43.66% representing 131 respondents indicated that they are highly aware or aware of the existence of the internet.

Table 2: Availability of digital information communication sources to rural dwellers in Ebonyi State

Item	HA		A		UA		HUA		Mean(X)	Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Internet	10	3.33	-	-	-	-	290	96.67	1.10	HUA
Desktop computer	10	3.33	-	-	-	-	290	96.67	1.10	HUA
Television	54	18	-	-	-	-	246	82	1.54	HUA
Radio	41	13.67	37	12.33	184	61.33	38	12.67	2.27	UA
Laptops,	6	2	-	-	-	-	294	98	1.06	HUA
Smart phones,	10	3.33	-	-	-	-	290	96.67	1.10	HUA
Smart television	-	-	-	-	-	-	300	100	1.00	HUA
Modem	10	3.33					290	96.67	1.10	HUA
Decoders	21	7	-	-	-	-	279	93	1.21	HUA
Digital Library	-	-	-	-	-	-	300	100	1.00	HUA
Telephone (GSM)	150	50	30	10	-	-	120	40	2.70	A
Community ICT Centre	-	-	-	-	-	-	300	100	1.00	HUA

*Key> HA=Highly Available, A=Available, UA=Unavailable, HUA=Highly Unavailable, Benchmark=2.50

On the availability of common and easy to handle digital information communication sources to the rural dwellers, the data in table 2 did reveal that 300 of the respondents representing 100% indicated highly unavailability of smart television, digital library and Community ICT Centre, while the same 100% indicated either highly unavailability or unavailability of internet, desktop computers, television, laptops, smart phones, Modems, as well as Decoders while 78 of the respondents or 26% agree to highly availability or availability of radio and 180 of the respondents or 60% indicated the availability of Telephone (GSM) which is the one of the two items that crossed the mean benchmark threshold of 2.50 while others failed below.

Table 3: Accessibility of digital information sources

Item	HA		A		IA		HIA		Mean(X)	Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Internet	***	***	***	***	***	***	300	100	1.00	HIA
Desktop computer	10	3.33	***	***	***	***	290	96.67	1.10	HIA
Television	8	2.67	32	10.67	54	18	206	68.67	1.47	HIA
Radio	241	80.33	***	***	***	***	59	19.67	3.41	HA
Laptops,	6	2	***	***	***	***	294	98	1.06	HIA
Smart phones,	10	3.33	***	***	***	***	290	96.67	1.10	HIA
Smart television	0	***	***	***	***	***	300	100	1.00	HIA
Modem	10	3.33	***	***	***	***	290	96.67	1.10	HIA
Decoders	21	7	***	***	***	***	279	93	1.21	HIA
Community Television viewing Centre	***	***	***	***	***	***	300	100	1.00	HIA
Library	***	***	***	***	***	***	300	100	1.00	HIA

Community ICT Centre	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	300	100	1.00	HIA
Telephone (GSM)	109	36.33	112	37.33	42	14	37	12.33	2.98		HA

*Key> HA=Highly Accessible, A=Accessible, IA=Inaccessible, HIA=Highly Inaccessible, Benchmark=2.50

As shown by the data collected as displayed in table 3 above, of the 13 items, only 2 sources are accessible to the rural dwellers. 300 which is 100% of the respondents expressed the highly inaccessibility of digital information sources such as the Internet, Smart television, Community Television viewing Centre, Library and Community ICT Centre, whereas, over 85% of the respondents indicated either highly inaccessibility or inaccessibility of desktop computers, modem, decoders as well as laptops. On the other hand, 241 or 80.33% indicated that radio is highly accessible and 73.66% or 221 of the respondents indicated either that Telephone (GSM) is highly accessible or accessible.

Figure 5: Reasons behind the utilization of Digital Information Technologies by the Rural Dwellers

The data as shown in figure 5 above is an aggregate of response of respondents in respect of the reasons behind the utilization of digital information gadgets and facilities. The data did show that 100% or the 300 respondents agree that they use them for personal pleasure, as tools of communication, for listening to news and for current awareness whereas, 257 of the respondents or 85.67 agree that it is being used for political awareness and only 34 or 11.33 and 35 or 11.67 agree that they are being used for research purposes and developmental enhancement.

Figure 6: Constraints in the Utilization of Digital Information Technologies by the Rural Dwellers

The data in figure 6 reveal that 100% or the 300 respondents agree that lack of awareness, lack of public power supply, lack of network, high cost of facilities, lack of commitment from government as well as absence of government owned ICT centres and libraries are major constraints in the utilization of digital information technologies by the rural dwellers, while 257 of the respondents or 85.67 attributed it to language barrier and 30% representing 85 of the respondents attributed it to lack of technological skills.

3.0. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The result of this study in the first instance substantiates the definition of rural dwellers as the culture of people studied and the state of where they live epitomize forgotten and rejected dwellers who have no hope of enjoying government sponsored and financed social infrastructures and amenities in the nearest future. Be that as it may, the study discovered that most dwellers of the rural communities studied are too far from the digital ecosystem as the data as shown in table 1 reveal that the people are highly unaware of the existence of most contemporary digital information technologies. This finding further buttresses the assertion of Olukoya (2002) who did state that despite the fact that about a million people have mobile phones, but internet use is lagging behind with only an estimated 20,000 to 30,000 Nigerians connected to the internet and inferred that the reason behind this was not far-fetched as over 120 million Nigerians are rural dwellers who can be said by implication excluded from partaking in the emerging information economy thereby not in reality with what is happening in the digital ecosystem. The inference is that twenty two years after this assertion, one can emphatically say, that the story has not changed in the rural areas of Nigeria despite dwellers witnessing the presence of mobile

communication masts being installed by mobile communication companies like Glo, Airtel, MTN and 9 Mobile.

The study also found that apart from radio and telephone (GSM) most digital information sources are highly unavailable for the rural dwellers to utilize. The study shows that digital information sources like smart television, digital library and Community ICT Centre, internet, desktop computers, television, laptops, smart phones, modems as well as decoders are out of the reach of the rural dwellers. The outcome of this study indeed brings to mind Adimorah (1990) research report that 80% of illiterate rural dwellers wallow in information deprivation.

The study further discovered that the rural dwellers do not have access to most contemporary digital information technologies. According to the findings, digital information sources such as the internet, smart television, Community television viewing Centre, Library and Community ICT Centre among others are highly inaccessible by the rural dwellers. This finding no doubt is contrary to the stand as expressed by Article 19 (2018) that information access is essential for individuals and communities to engage government to improve public services, citizens to know their rights to public services and what resources are available to them as well as monitoring how effectively governments and authorities are providing vital services and holding them to account as well as UNESCO (2022) declaration that access to Information is a key driver for the achievement of the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable development and in particular SDG Goal 16 that promotes just, peaceful and inclusive societies

Furtherance, the study found that rural dwellers like anyone else have their reasons for utilizing any digital information source, gadget or facility which include for personal pleasure, as tools of communication, for listening to news and for current and political awareness and as well as for developmental enhancement among others (see fig. 5). This outcome is not far from Asemah (2011) inference that rural dwellers need accurate information that will enable them to live and appreciate the activities of the government in power after all, they are involved in the task of feeding the nation, therefore need information on several issues including information on loan opportunities offered by government and how to dispose their farm proceeds as well as information about health care, weather, family planning, agricultural inputs among others.

It was further discovered that that lack of awareness, lack of public power supply, lack of network (internet connectivity), high cost of digital information facilities such as smart phones, computers and modems, lack of commitment from government as well as absence of government owned ICT centres and libraries are major constraints in the utilization of digital information technologies by the rural dwellers though not restricted to the above factors as can be seen in figure 6. This finding is far cry from the claims of Nigerian Communication Commission (NCC) in her mandate to promote the provision of modern, universal, efficient, reliable, affordable and easily accessible communications services and the widest range thereof throughout Nigeria (Nigerian Communication Commission, 2024).

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The outcome of this study may be said to be an exposition debunking many claims by government and her agencies, the Nigerian Communication Commission and others in respect of the well-being of rural dwellers in Nigeria as the situation is not peculiar to Ebonyi State rural communities rather it a microcosm of the macrocosm of the real state of rural dwellers in Nigeria and even in some cases, worse. Nigerian developmental policies should be truth based and not bilabial and paper based to project the nation in good light in the comity of nations while the rural populace wallows in abject poverty and deprivation in a world ruled by information and driven by digital technologies. If the UN-SDGs goals with the priority to eradicate poverty among rural dwellers and make life worth living for them, is to be realized in Nigeria, there is the urgent need for government to change her attitude and think rural and instead deceitful urban oriented projects that have no impact on the well-being of the rural dwellers and ensure access to information, internet and computer services as to increasing rural dwellers knowledge on various opportunities available in the global ecosystem. In this regard, this study suggests that:

- i. All the identified constraints in the utilization of digital information sources, facilities and gadgets should be tackled by government and her concerned agencies head-on in line with the mandate of NCC which is to promote the provision of modern, universal, efficient, reliable, affordable and easily accessible communications services and the widest range thereof throughout Nigeria.
- ii. Government should as a matter of necessity and a thing of national importance mandate NCC to make internet access available to the rural communities at no or low cost and if possible distribute laptops to them.
- iii. As a follow up to the above suggestion, government with concerned agencies should provide mandatory ICT training program designed for both male and female rural dwellers regardless of the occupation with a view to increasing their economic wellbeing through the acquisition of technology skills thereby making them relevant in the digital ecosystem.
- iv. In the area of electricity or lack of public power supply, if government is not willing to have the rural communities connected to the national power grid, there is today alternative power source, the solar energy; such communities should be hooked to the solar power through the installations of solar panels as obtained in developed nations.
- v. Furthermore, all three-tiers of government should ensure that public libraries are established in every rural community (equipped with state-of-the-art facilities) as with this, information materials can easily be made available to the people and the people will have a breath of government presence both educationally and recreationally. This is built on the fact that libraries as social institutions ensure that information and the skills to use it are available to all and sundry which project them as critical institutions for all in this digital age. In this digital ecosystem, libraries also provide information and communication technology infrastructure, assist people develop the capacity to effectively and efficiently utilize information as well as preserve information to ensure ongoing access for future generation. Apart from the above roles, libraries further provide an established, trusted network of local institutions that effectively reach new and marginalized population like the rural dwellers. Let it be drummed that access to information is a crosscutting issue that supports SDGs. Libraries can support rural dwellers

by providing access to information, supporting literacy and ICT skills and access to community space.

- vi. Finally, the use of local languages (dialect) should be encouraged while broadcasting any program on radio and television as a way of sensitization and creation of awareness of the uses of such media of communication and how irresistible and relevant they are as sources of information.

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